

The yield potential of three crosses between diverse parents of indica type

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A widespread belief exists that the yield of indica cultivars grown in the lowland tropics has reached a barrier of 10 t ha⁻¹ because of the narrow genetic base of modern varieties. We tested this hypothesis by evaluating the yield potential of the crosses between high-yielding Sri Lankan varieties and high-yielding IRRRI varieties: Bg34-8/IR58 (cross 1; 3-mo duration), Bg94-1/IR62 (cross 2; 3 1/2 mo duration) and Bg90-2/IR72 (cross 3; 4 1/2 mo duration). Individuals raised were of the basic generations (P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, B₁, and B₂) and F₃ and triple testcross families (F₂ × P₁, F₂ × P₂, and F₂ × F₁) of each of these pedigrees in three completely randomized experiments, one for each cross.

Each of the 14 characters scored was heritable. Estimates of the heritability of grain yield, obtained from F₃ families for

crosses 1, 2, and 3, were 0.29, 0.38 and 0.51, and for 1,000-grain weight over 0.57, 0.58, and 0.70, respectively. Though this was significant only in cross 1, the F₁ mean exceeded that of the best parent in all three crosses for grain yield. The dominance ratio, (H/D)^{1/2}, which was less than one in each cross, indicated that the increasing genes for this character were dispersed between the parents. Predictions of the proportion of recombinant inbred lines that could be extracted by single seed descent from each cross, the performance of which exceeds that of the best parent, showed that it should be relatively easy to obtain such lines from each cross for the majority of characters, including grain yield and 1,000-grain weight.

Estimates of genetic correlations between characters varied considerably over crosses, suggesting that their major cause is the linkage disequilibrium of linked genes rather than pleiotropy. Grain yield was strongly and positively correlated (r ≥ 0.7) with tiller and panicle number, days to heading, height at flowering, and panicle weight in cross 3. However, in cross 2, grain yield was only strongly and positively correlated with number of grains panicle⁻¹ and panicle weight, and in cross 1, with tiller number and panicle number. Results suggest that it should be possible to identify

crosses in a breeding program from which recombinant inbred lines can be extracted that are superior for any combination of traits of a desired multiple phenotype. Upon examining the means of the 38-40 F₃ families raised in these experiments, one or more families achieved the desired target for each of the majority of characters, including grain yield in all three crosses. Evidence of transgressive variation for characters of interest as early as the F₃ generation leaves little doubt about their potential to produce superior inbred lines.

The mean grain yield of the best F₃ family, cross 3, which is in the same age group as the new plant type, was 154.4 g. The predicted yield was 9.7 t ha⁻¹, which is appreciably better than the predicted yield of 8.3 t ha⁻¹ for the best parent of this cross, Bg90-2.

Results from this investigation are inconsistent with the belief that the apparent yield barrier of indica cultivars is due to a narrow genetic base. This suggests that the inability of breeders to breach this barrier is because of other causes, including inefficient breeding procedures and employing indirect visual selection when attempting to obtain improvement for several quantitative characters simultaneously. ■

Stability analysis of 13 early-duration upland rice genotypes in Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Nearly 0.24 million ha of upland rice is grown in Bastar Plateau Zone in Madhya Pradesh during wet season (June-September). Traditional, low-yielding cultivars are dominant in the zone. Suitable upland early rice varieties need to be identified.

We evaluated 13 early-duration rice genotypes for grain yield and morpho-agronomic attributes. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1990-92 wet seasons. Each genotype was direct seeded in ten 5-m long rows using 25-cm spacing. We recorded plant height, panicle length, fertile grains panicle⁻¹, and percentage spikelet fertility for five randomly selected plants from each plot of every replication. Days to flowering, days to maturity, and grain yield were computed for each plot. Number of panicle-bearing tillers m⁻² from a randomly selected 1-m² plot was recorded. Means were used for stability analysis over three environments following the method of Ebberhart and Russel (1966).

Table 1. Mean grain yield (t ha⁻¹) and estimates of stability parameters for 13 rice genotypes across three environments. Jagdalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1990-92.

Genotype	x	b	s ² d
R.281 PP 31-1	1.64	0.88	2.84
RWR 78-71-9	1.97	1.33	4.44
JR80-4-6	1.56	1.34	1.16
JR84-7-1-19	2.19	0.78	8.75
RNR1446	2.07	1.17	-5.88
Culture 1	1.66	-0.03***	-6.59
Poorva	1.34	0.11**	-6.55
Annada	2.55	1.85**	-4.72
Tulasi	2.37	2.01**	-4.75
Rasi	2.19	1.95**	4.22
Aditya	2.14	0.89	3.68
Tellahamsa	2.19	0.87	-0.06
Badoldhan (L)	1.97	-0.16**	-6.28
av		1.99	

*** = significant at the 1% level.